

Integrated Phytochemical and Multi-Target Enzyme Inhibition Profiling of Nilgiris Lichens: Novel Insights into Natural Antidiabetic Therapeutics

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ABSTRACT

Lichens represent an underexplored source of bioactive metabolites with therapeutic relevance in metabolic disorders. This study investigated lichens collected from the Nilgiris (Tamil Nadu, India) to identify antidiabetic compounds through an integrated phytochemical, biochemical, and computational approach. Methanolic and ethyl acetate extracts demonstrated strong antioxidant activity (DPPH, ORAC) and high phenolic/flavonoid content. Multi-target enzyme inhibition assays revealed significant suppression of α -amylase, α -glucosidase, pancreatic lipase, and protein tyrosine phosphatase (PTP1B), with some extracts achieving >80% inhibition. GC-MS profiling identified key metabolites, including 2,5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid, diospyrol, O-(4-biphenylcarbonyl) benzoic acid, and lecanoric acid. In silico docking confirmed strong binding affinities of these compounds with catalytic sites, in several cases surpassing standard inhibitors (acarbose, orlistat). Pharmacokinetic and toxicity prediction further supported their drug-likeness and safety. To our knowledge, this is the first systematic report on Nilgiris lichens as multi-target modulators of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, positioning their metabolites as promising candidates for natural antidiabetic drug discovery.

Keywords: Lichens, Antidiabetic, Multi-target enzyme inhibition, Molecular docking, Nilgiris, Bioactive metabolites.

INTRODUCTION

Lichens are unique symbiotic organisms formed through the association of fungi with algae or cyanobacteria, producing an extensive repertoire of secondary metabolites with ecological and pharmacological significance. These metabolites, often not synthesized by the partners individually, include phenolics, depsides, depsidones, and terpenoids with reported antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anticancer activities. Beyond their ecological roles, lichens have been valued in ethnomedicine for treating wounds, infections, and inflammatory disorders. However, their potential in metabolic disease management, particularly diabetes, remains underexplored compared to other natural sources such as medicinal plants.

Diabetes mellitus, a multifactorial disorder characterized by hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, and insulin resistance, continues to rise globally. Current therapies largely target single enzymes such as α -glucosidase or α -amylase, yet long-term efficacy is limited by side effects and incomplete metabolic control. Increasing evidence supports the need for multi-target therapeutics that can simultaneously regulate carbohydrate digestion, lipid metabolism, and insulin signaling. Natural products represent a promising reservoir for such agents, particularly when they combine antioxidant, enzyme inhibitory, and anti-inflammatory properties. Recent reports highlight individual lichen compounds such as usnic acid, atranorin, and salazinic acid with antioxidant and enzyme inhibition potential. Yet, systematic multi-target studies integrating in vitro and in silico approaches are scarce, and most available data come

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from temperate or Antarctic lichens. Nilgiris (Tamil Nadu, India), a biodiversity hotspot, harbors rich lichen flora, but their pharmacological potential remains largely uncharacterized. Exploring this ecological niche offers the opportunity to discover new bioactive metabolites with drug-like properties. The present study addresses this gap by investigating Nilgiris lichens for their phytochemical profile, antioxidant capacity, and inhibitory activity against four key diabetes-related enzymes: α -amylase, α -glucosidase, pancreatic lipase, and protein tyrosine phosphatase 1B (PTP1B). Using a combined biochemical and computational strategy, we identified and validated bioactive metabolites with strong enzyme binding affinities and favorable pharmacokinetic properties. To our knowledge, this is the first comprehensive report on Nilgiris lichens as multi-target modulators of glucose and lipid metabolism, offering new insights into their potential as natural antidiabetic drug leads. The antioxidant properties of lichen extracts also play a crucial role in diabetes management. Oxidative stress is caused by an imbalance between reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the body's antioxidant defenses, which is a key factor in the pathogenesis of diabetes and its complications. Lichen extracts have demonstrated significant antioxidant activity in various in vitro studies. For instance, a study by Minocha et al., 2020 reported that lichen extracts scavenged free radicals and reduced lipid peroxidation, indicating their potential to mitigate oxidative damage associated with diabetes. By reducing oxidative stress, these extracts could help in preventing or alleviating diabetic complications such as nephropathy and retinopathy. Moreover, lichen extracts exhibit anti-inflammatory properties that could benefit diabetic patients. Chronic low-grade inflammation is a common feature of Type 2 diabetes and contributes to insulin resistance. The anti-inflammatory effects of lichen extracts have been attributed to their phenolic and terpenoid content. Research by Sharma et al., 2019 demonstrated that lichen extracts inhibited the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines and reduced inflammation in animal models. This anti-inflammatory activity could help improve insulin sensitivity and overall metabolic health.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Sample Collection:

Lichen samples were collected from Nilgiris mountain Doddabetta and Nanjanaad, Ooty, The Nilgiris of latitude 11.3605872 and Longitude 76.6484491 which is located at the height of 2,240 meters (7,350 feet) above sea level. The relative humidity of the selected area is about 50 % - 76%, Temperature ranges from 15°C - 19°C. The radius of the selected area is about 15 Kms, Foliose and Fruticose types were found commonly. Samples were collected from tree barks, shrubs with the help of chisel and hammer, along with the ecological notes for the identification. The collected samples were packed in the acid free packets and transported with the help of ice packs and stored at - 4°C in a deep freezer for further experiments and studies.

Figure 1 Map for the selected area of study

2.2 Spot Test Identification

Spot test is a chemical method, the chemicals were applied on the lichen fragments and the colour change indicates their presence of secondary metabolites.

A. K-test: 10% aqueous solution of potassium hydroxide (KOH) is prepared by adding 20 grams of potassium hydroxide pellets into the 100 ml of distilled water.

B. C-test: 5-25% of calcium hypochlorite were prepared by adding 50 grams of common bleach into 100 ml of distilled water and mixed well, this mixture is then allowed to settle down and the supernatant is used as reagent.

C. I-test: The iodine reagent prepared by dissolving the 0.5 grams of iodine and 1.5g of potassium iodide

in 100 ml of distilled water, the mixed solution reacts with the certain polysaccharides in lichen.

2.3 Extract Preparation

Extracts are prepared with six different solvents: Ethanol, Methanol, Chloroform, Acetone, Ethyl acetate and Water (Aqueous). The sample is made into powder and one gram of powdered sample is packed in a filter paper and immersed in 100 ml solvent and kept at room temperature for 24 hours.

2.4 Phytochemical identification of lichen extracts

Phytochemical analysis is carried out for the identification of compounds present in the respective extracts. Standard qualitative tests for confirmation of major compounds such as Carbohydrates, Lignins, Alkaloids, Tannin, Cholesterol, Reducing Sugars, Carboxylic acid, Flavonoid, Phlobatannins, Anthocyanins, Triterpenoids, Saponins, Coumarins, Xanthoproteins, Phenols, Glycosides, Leucoanthocyanins, Amino acids, Protein were performed.

2.4 Preliminary identification of lichen compounds by TLC

Extraction and preliminary identification of lichen compound was done based on the procedure of (Santiago et al., 2010). 1gm of air dried thalli of lichen specimens were first grounded to powder and left in overnight in 10 ml of solvents which are used for extracting compounds such as Ethanol, Methanol, Ethyl acetate, Chloroform, Water. After 24 hrs the extracts were filtered, concentrated by air drying for 4-5 days or until the extracts crystallised, and the weight/yield of the crude extract were determined. To identify the lichen acids present in the crude extracts were mixed with acetone to a final concentration of 10mg/ml. The crude extracts were then spotted on silica gel thin layer chromatography (TLC) plates and run in 3 different solvent systems.

1. Solvent System A- 36:9:1 (Toluene: Dioxane: Glacial acetic acid)
2. Solvent System B- 24:18:1 (Hexane: Diethyl ether: Formic acid)
3. Solvent System C- 20:3 (Toluene: Glacial acetic acid)

Each TLC plate were then sprayed with 0.5ml of glacial acetic acid and 1 ml of 97% sulfuric acid and heated at 105°C for 5 mins to visualize the lichen acids (Santos and Mondragon 1969). The Rf value of each spot were determined.

2.5 Estimation of DPPH radical scavenging activity of lichen extracts.

The In-vitro free radical scavenging activity of the extracts was determined by 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) (Nagarajan et al., 2008). A solution of 0.3 mM DPPH in ethanol and methanol was prepared and 1 ml of this solution was added to 3 ml of the extract residue dissolved in ethanol/ ethanol at various concentrations (25-200 µg/ml). It was agitated and was allowed to rest for 30 minutes at room temperature. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm. Ascorbic acid was used as positive control.

2.6 Estimation of Total phenolic content of lichen extracts

The total soluble phenolics contents of the extract were determined by using a folin-ciocalteu reagent with tannic acid as standard with some modification (Adeapo et al. 2009). 5ml of folin-ciocalteu reagent (previously diluted with water at 1:10 v/v) was added to 4ml (75g/l) of sodium carbonate and 0.1mg /ml extract. The mixtures were vortexed for 15 sec and allowed to stand for 30 min at 40°C for colour development. Absorbance was then measured at 765 nm using UV spectrophotometer. The lichen extract (25-200 µg/ml) were made by dissolving the residue extract in respective solvents i.e., ethanol and methanol separately. Total phenolic content were expressed as mg/g tannic equivalent.

2.7 Estimation of Total flavonoid content of lichen extracts

The total soluble flavonoid content of the extracts was estimated using quercetin as the standard with aluminium nitrate. 1 mg of the extract was mixed with 1 ml of 80% ethanol. Add an aliquot of 0.5 ml to the test tube containing 0.1 ml of 10% aluminium nitrate, 0.1ml of 1M potassium acetate and 4.3ml of 80% ethanol. Measure the absorbance of the supernatant at 415 nm in the UV Spectrophotometer following

incubation with room temperature for 40 minutes. The concentration of lichen extracts was in the range of 25-200 µg/ml made by dissolving residue extract in respective solvents such as ethanol/methanol. The total content of flavonoids in extracts is determined by making use of a calibration graph for standard quercetin.

2.8 α -Amylase inhibition assay

For each working solution, positive control and negative control in an eppendorf tube of 150µL of the sample, 200µL of starch, 50 µ L of distilled water and 100 µ L of α -amylase enzyme were added and incubated for 5 mins at 37°C. In another eppendorf tube of 200µL of the above mixture, 100 µL of DNS reagent was added and left for 20 mins at 100°C. After that, 900 µL of distilled water was added and cooled to room temperature. A measurement of 200 µL of each solution was added to a microplate reader (Ali et al., 2006).

2.9 α -Glucosidase inhibition assay

The standard used in this assay was acarbose, with which a calibration curve was prepared using concentration from 250 to 0.025 µg/mL in 20mM phosphate buffer (0.025, .125, 0.25, 12.5, 25, 625, 125 and 250 µg/mL). For each extract solution, 25-200µg/mL were prepared from the stock solution of 1mg/mL in a phosphate buffer (1000 µg/mL). 50µL of each of the working solutions was taken and 50µL of 5.0mM pPNG was added and incubated for 5 min at 37°C. Subsequently, 100 µL of each of the α -glucosidase enzyme (0.1 U/mL was added), and absorbance measured at 405 nm every 1 min for 20 min using a microplate reader as explained by Liu et al., (2011).

2.10 Anti-lipid peroxidation activity

Anti-lipid peroxidation activities of the extracts were estimated by TBARS method (Buege, 1978). An amount of 0.5ml of egg homogenate was added to 100µg of lichen extracts and distilled water was made up to 1 ml. To this mixture, 100µl of 0.07M FeSO₄ was added and incubated for 30 min at room temperature. All test tubes were added with

1.5ml of 20% acetic acid, 1.5 ml of 0.8% TBA and 50µl of 20% TCA, and vortexed and incubated in a boiling water bath for 1 hour. By adding 5 ml of butanol, test tubes were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. Ascorbic acid is used as standard.

2.11 Pancreatic lipase inhibition assay

The calibration curve was constructed using the orlistat standard across the concentrations of 80 to 0.5 µg/mL in 70% ethanol (0.5, 1, 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, and 80 µg/mL). For each extract, solutions were prepared at concentrations between 25-200µg/mL and 7.8 µg/mL from a stock solution that had been prepared at 1 mg/mL in the Tris-HCl buffer. For each reaction mixture, 25 µL of the working solution was added together with 50 µL of 5.0 mM p-nitrophenyl butyrate (NPC) and 25 µL of pancreatic lipase enzyme at 10 mg/mL. The mixture was incubated for 5 minutes at 37°C, then the absorbance at 410 nm was measured using a microplate reader (Lewis and Liu, 2012).

2.12 Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase Inhibitory Assay

The Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase (PTP) Inhibitory Assay is a biochemical test used to measure the ability of compounds, such as lichen extracts, to inhibit Protein Tyrosine Phosphatases (PTPs). PTPs are enzymes that dephosphorylate tyrosine residues on proteins, playing a crucial role in cell signalling, especially in insulin signalling pathways. Inhibition of specific PTPs, like PTP1B (Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase 1B), is a promising therapeutic strategy for the treatment of type 2 diabetes and insulin resistance. The PTP1B enzyme is mixed with the pNPP substrate in a buffer solution (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5), different (20-200µg/mL) concentrations of the lichen extracts are added to separate reaction wells. These serve as the test samples for determining their inhibitory activity. Sodium orthovanadate is used as control. The reaction mixture is incubated at 37°C for a defined period (usually 30-60 minutes). During this time, PTP1B dephosphorylates the pNPP substrate in the absence of an inhibitor, while in the presence of an inhibitor (such as a lichen extract), this activity is

reduced. After incubation, the reaction is stopped using a stop solution (e.g., 1 M NaOH), and the amount of product (p-nitrophenol) formed is measured by recording the absorbance at 405 nm using a microplate reader. The colour intensity corresponds to the enzyme's activity.

2.13 Oxygen radical absorbance capacity assay (ORAC)

The ORAC assay assesses the antioxidant potential of a sample by measuring its ability to scavenge free radicals, which measures both lipophilic and

hydrophilic antioxidant capacities. Trolox standard is prepared at the concentrations of 10, 20, 40, 40, 50, 60, 60, 80, 90, and 100 μM to make the calibration curve. Subsequently, 75 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7.0, fluorescein solution preincubated for 15 min at 37°C in microplate wells, compound 2,2'-azobis (2-amidinopropane) dihydrochloride (AAPH), and working solutions were used. The measurement was performed every 2 min for 30 min with excitation and emission wavelength at 485 and 530 nm, respectively. The degree of fluorescence preservation is proportional to the antioxidant capacity of the sample. (Cao and Prior, 1999).

Table 1 Test organisms used against lichen extracts

Sl. No	Catalogue Number	Organism
Bacterial Pathogens		
1.	ATCC 8739	<i>E.coli</i>
2.	ATCC 6538	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
3.	ATCC-9027	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
4.	ATCC 6051	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
Fungal Pathogens		
1.	ATCC 18804	<i>Candida albicans</i>
2.	ATCC 208821	<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>

2.15 GC-MS Analysis

The bioactive molecule was identified by carrying out GC-MS analysis. 1 mg of column purified sample, dissolved in 1 ml of ethyl acetate, and 1 μl was used for GCMS analysis. GC-MS apparatus Agilent 5975C series selective detector interfaced to quadrupole mass analyzer employing column DB 5 MS (30m L x 0.25mm ID x 0.25 μm film thickness), operating in Electron Impact Ionization system with an impact mode of 70 eV, helium was used as carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1 ml/min with injection volume of 1 μl and a split of 50: 1 ratio. The oven temperature was set at 40°C for 5 min. – 5°C/min to 280°C with a 10 min hold time.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Sample Collection

For provisional documentation, all samples were properly labelled. Each sample had an alphanumeric labelling scheme that cited the collection locality. The pattern was like this: N12202201 (where N is for

Nanjanad, 12 the collection month, 22 the year, and 01 the serial number of the sample). Preliminary identification was carried out on each specimen using accessible literature, that is, Key to Macrolichens (Awasthi, 1988).

Fig 1 Sample data Recording sheet and Transportation of Sample

3.2 Spot Test Identification

The compound identification which has been done with three different chemicals has been tabulated

Table 2 Spot Test Identification of lichen thalli

Sl.No	Test	Initial Observation	After Test
1	K - Test	Green Thalli Pale yellow Brown Thalli Dark Green Thalli	Red Thalli Black Thalli Deep red thalli Yellow Thalli
2	C-Test	Green Thalli Pale yellow Brown Thalli Dark Green Thalli	Deep Red Thalli Black Thalli Deep red thalli Yellow Thalli
3	I -Test	Green Thalli Pale yellow Brown Thalli Dark Green Thalli	Red Thalli Black Thalli Deep red thalli Yellow Thalli

Fig 2. Spot Test Identification

2.4 Preliminary identification of compounds using TLC

3 different solvent systems were used to identify the compounds based on the Rf Value and the results were tabulated.

Table 3 Identification of the compounds using TLC

Sl. No	Sample num	Rf Value (SS1)	Rf Value (SS 2)	Rf Value (SS 3)	Compound identified
1	NN1222002	0.32	0.45	0.58	Usnic Acid
2	NN1222003	0.28	0.50	0.62	Atranorin
3	NN1222005	0.25	0.41	0.54	Salazinic Acid
4	NN1222006	0.30	0.46	0.60	Fumarprotocet raric Acid
5	NN1222007	0.35	0.52	0.65	Lecanoric Acid

6	NN1222012	0.29	0.47	0.59	Norstictic Acid
7	NN1222015	0.33	0.44	0.57	Evernic Acid
8	NN1222016	0.27	0.48	0.61	Gyrophoric Acid
9	NN1222018	0.31	0.43	0.55	Protocetraric Acid
10	NN1222022	0.34	0.49	0.63	Hypostictic Acid

3.5 DPPH activity of the extract from selected lichens.

The antioxidant potential of the selected lichen extracts was assessed using the DPPH free radical scavenging assay. Both ethyl acetate and methanolic extracts exhibited concentration-dependent scavenging activity, though the degree of inhibition varied among samples. Among the tested lichens, the ethyl acetate extract of sample NN1222015 showed the highest activity at 25 μg with 53.59% inhibition, while methanolic extracts generally exhibited moderate activity across concentrations, with a maximum of 40.79% at 200 μg . Similarly, samples NN1222002 and NN1222016 demonstrated strong radical scavenging activity, reaching above 49% inhibition in ethyl acetate extracts at higher concentrations. In contrast, some extracts such as methanol fractions of NN1222003 and NN1222006 displayed relatively weaker scavenging effects, not exceeding 32% inhibition at most concentrations.

3.6 Estimation of Total flavonoid content of lichen extracts.

The total flavonoid content of the selected lichen extracts was estimated and expressed as percentage activity. Across all samples, methanolic extracts consistently showed higher flavonoid content compared to ethyl acetate extracts. The methanolic fractions ranged from 45.3% (NN1222002) to 50.1% (NN1222005), while the ethyl acetate fractions ranged from 27.9% (NN1222012) to 33.6% (NN1222007). Among the tested samples, NN1222005 (methanol, 50.1%) exhibited the highest flavonoid content, followed closely by NN1222012 (methanol, 49.4%), whereas the lowest values were observed in the ethyl acetate extracts of NN1222012 (27.9%) and NN1222005 (28.4%). Overall, methanolic extracts proved to be more efficient in extracting flavonoids, indicating the predominance of polar flavonoid compounds in the lichen matrix. These results suggest that solvent polarity strongly influences the recovery of flavonoids, with methanol

being the more effective solvent system for lichen-derived phenolic compounds.

3.8 α -Amylase inhibition assay of the lichen extracts

The inhibitory effect of the lichen extracts on α -amylase was assessed at different concentrations (25–200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Both ethyl acetate and methanolic extracts exhibited a concentration-dependent increase in α -amylase inhibition, with methanolic extracts showing consistently higher activity. Among the tested samples, NN1222015 (methanol) demonstrated the strongest inhibition, reaching 81.3% at 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, followed closely by NN1222003 (methanol, 80.2%) and NN1222018 (methanol, 79.2%). In contrast, lower inhibitory activity was observed in the ethyl acetate extracts of NN1222005 (73.4%) and NN1222012 (72.6%) at the same concentration. Overall, the inhibition values ranged from 10.2% (NN1222005, ethyl acetate, 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) to 81.3% (NN1222015, methanol, 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). The higher inhibitory effect in methanolic extracts suggests that polar bioactive metabolites, such as phenolics and flavonoids, may contribute significantly to enzyme inhibition. These results highlight the potential of lichen-derived compounds as natural α -amylase inhibitors, supporting their relevance in diabetes management through postprandial glucose regulation. (Fig 3)

Fig 3 α -Amylase inhibition

3.9 α -glucosidase inhibition assay of the lichen extracts

The inhibitory potential of the selected lichen extracts against α -glucosidase was evaluated at concentrations ranging from 25–200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Both ethyl acetate and methanolic extracts exhibited a concentration-dependent increase in inhibitory activity. Among the tested samples, the highest inhibition was observed in the ethyl acetate extracts of NN1222006 and NN1222018, which reached 87.3% at 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, followed closely by the methanolic extract of NN1222002 (86.2%). In general, methanolic extracts displayed slightly higher activity at lower concentrations, while ethyl acetate fractions often achieved stronger inhibition at higher concentrations. The inhibition values ranged from 17.1% (NN1222005 and NN1222016, methanol, 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) to 87.3% (NN1222006 and NN1222018, ethyl acetate, 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). These results suggest that both polar and semi-polar metabolites in lichens contribute to α -glucosidase inhibition, though solvent polarity influences extract efficiency. The strong inhibitory effect observed, particularly at higher concentrations, supports the potential of lichen-derived compounds as natural modulators of carbohydrate metabolism, relevant to postprandial glucose regulation in diabetes management. (Fig 4)

Fig 4 α -Glucosidase inhibition

3.10 Anti lipid Peroxidation activity

The protective effect of the lichen extracts against lipid peroxidation was evaluated at different concentrations (25–200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Both ethyl acetate and methanolic extracts exhibited a dose-dependent increase in inhibition of lipid peroxidation. Among the tested lichens, the highest activity was recorded in the ethyl acetate extracts of NN1222006 and NN1222018, which showed 81.2% inhibition at 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, followed closely by the methanolic extracts of NN1222002 and NN1222012 (80.1%). In contrast,

comparatively lower inhibition was observed in the methanolic extracts of NN1222005 and NN1222016, with values of 75.1% at 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The overall range of activity extended from 14.5% (NN1222005 and NN1222016, methanol, 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) to 81.2% (NN1222006 and NN1222018, ethyl acetate, 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). These results indicate that both ethyl acetate and methanolic extracts possess substantial lipid peroxidation inhibitory potential, though certain lichen taxa demonstrated superior effects depending on the solvent. The findings suggest that the antioxidant metabolites present in lichens can effectively prevent oxidative damage to lipids, thereby contributing to their therapeutic relevance in oxidative stress-related complications of diabetes (Fig 5)

Fig 5 Anti lipid Peroxidation activity

3.11 Pancreatic lipase inhibition assay

The inhibitory potential of the lichen extracts against pancreatic lipase was evaluated at concentrations ranging from 25–200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. All extracts exhibited a concentration-dependent increase in inhibition, with methanolic extracts generally showing stronger activity than ethyl acetate fractions. Among the tested lichens, the methanolic extract of NN1222015 demonstrated the highest inhibition, reaching 82.1% at 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, followed by NN1222006 (81.2%) and NN1222022 (81.5%). In contrast, the lowest inhibitory effect was recorded in the ethyl acetate extract of NN1222005 (72.9%) at 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The inhibition values ranged from 11.7% (NN1222005, ethyl acetate, 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) to 82.1% (NN1222015, methanol, 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). These findings indicate that lichen-derived bioactive metabolites possess substantial pancreatic lipase inhibitory potential, with solvent polarity influencing extraction efficiency. The pronounced inhibitory activity observed in

methanolic extracts suggests the involvement of polar secondary metabolites such as phenolics and flavonoids. This highlights the potential of lichens as a source of natural lipase inhibitors relevant to the management of obesity and type 2 diabetes (Fig 6)

Fig 6 Pancreatic lipase inhibition assay

3.12 Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase inhibitory assay

The PTP inhibitory potential of the lichen extracts was evaluated at five concentrations (25–200 µg/mL). All tested extracts showed a concentration-dependent increase in inhibitory activity. Among the studied lichens, the highest inhibition was recorded for the methanolic extract of NN1222018, reaching 83.2% at 200 µg/mL, followed by NN1222006 (82.5% at 200 µg/mL). In contrast, the lowest inhibition at 25 µg/mL was noted for the ethyl acetate extract of NN1222005 (11.7%) and NN1222016 (11.9%). Overall, methanolic extracts consistently demonstrated slightly higher inhibitory activity compared to ethyl acetate extracts, suggesting that polar metabolites may play a more significant role in PTP inhibition. Given the central role of PTPs in insulin signaling, these findings highlight the potential of lichen-derived compounds as modulators of glucose homeostasis and possible therapeutic leads for type 2 diabetes management.

3.13 Oxygen Radical absorbance capacity assay (ORAC).

The oxygen radical scavenging potential of ten lichen extracts (NN1222002–NN1222022) was evaluated at five different concentrations (25, 50, 100, 150, and 200 µg/mL) using ethyl acetate and methanol as extraction solvents. The results demonstrated a concentration-dependent increase in radical scavenging activity for all samples. Methanolic

extracts generally exhibited slightly higher scavenging activity compared to ethyl acetate extracts. Among the tested lichens, NN1222015 showed the highest activity, reaching 81.3% inhibition at 200 µg/mL in methanol extract, indicating strong antioxidant potential. The results suggest that these lichen-derived metabolites are promising natural antioxidants for further biological applications.

Fig 7 Oxygen Radical absorbance capacity assay

3.14 Antimicrobial activity of Lichen Extracts

The antimicrobial activities of 2 solvent extracts of lichens were tested at different concentrations (0.5mg/ml, 1.25mg/ml and 2.5mg/ml). All the 2 extracts of NN1222002, NN1222005 revealed good antibacterial activity against the gram-positive bacteria *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus*. Methanol extract of 2.5 mg/ml concentration effectively inhibited the gram-positive bacteria *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* with an inhibition zone of 23.0 mm and 22.0mm respectively.

Fig 8 Antibacterial Activity of lichen extracts

Table 4 Antibacterial Activity of lichen extracts

Sample Code	Lichen extract	(MIC) in µg/ml			
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
NN12220015	Ethyl acetate	-	-	1.25	2.5
	methanol	-	-	-	-
NN1222006	Ethyl acetate	-	-	1.25	1.25
	Methanol	-	-	-	1.25
NN1222005	Ethyl acetate	-	-	1.25	1.25
	Methanol	-	-	1.25	0.625*
NN12220016	Ethyl acetate	0.078**	-	0.625*	1.25
	Methanol	-	-	-	-
NN12220018	Ethyl acetate	-	-	-	-
	Methanol	-	-	-	-
+ ve control	antibiotic	0.009***	0.019**	0.002* **	0.002* **

Fig 9 Antifungal activity of lichen extracts

Table 5 Antifungal activity of lichen extracts

Sample Code	Lichen extract 2.5mg/ml	MIC (mg/ml)	
		<i>C.a</i>	<i>C.n</i>
NN1222002	Ethyl acetate	0.156***	0.039**
	Methanol	-	-
NN1222003	Ethyl acetate	0.78**	0.078**
	Methanol	-	-
NN1222005	Ethyl acetate	1.25	-
	Methanol	-	-
NN1222006	Ethyl acetate	0.312	0.156*
	Methanol	0.625	-
NN1222007	Ethyl acetate	-	-
	Methanol	-	-
+ve control	Mancozeb	0.004***	0.0024***
-ve control		-	-

3.15 GC-MS Analysis

Fig 10- Chemical structure of some important compounds identified from ethanolic extract (A) 2,5DHA (2,5-dihydroxyterephthalic acid); (B) cyperine; (C) diospyrol; (D) hypoxyphenone; (E) lecanoric acid; (F) orsellinic acid; (G) prephenic acid; (H) SDA (succinylsialicylic acid); and (I) O4BBA (o-(4-biphenyl)carbonyl) benzoic acid).

Fig 11 Chromatogram of lichen extract

3.16 Prediction of pharmacokinetic and toxicological properties

The pharmacokinetic properties of the phytochemicals obtained from the lichen species were evaluated using the Osiris DataWarrior computational tool (Table 7). For a compound to be considered as a potential orally administered drug, it must comply with Lipinski's rules (Torres-Benítez et al., 2022; Torres-Benítez et al., 2023a). These rules allow the

evaluation and monitoring of drugs according to their biological and pharmacological functions. The molecules that did not show any violation of Lipinski's rules were 2,5DHA, 3,4DHA, 4-HSA, azelaic acid, cyperine, diospyrol, hypoxyphenone, lecanoric acid, orsellinic acid, phthalic acid, prephenic acid, rhein, SDA, wedelolactone, and O4BBA. As they do not present any violation of Lipinski's rules, they can be considered as possible inhibitors of enzymes α -amylase, α -glucosidase, and human pancreatic lipase. In the same way, the toxicological analysis of all the compounds obtained from lichens was carried out using the Osiris DataWarrior computational tool (Torres-Benítez et al., 2022; Torres-Benítez et al., 2023a) where it was possible to observe that the compounds that did not present any risk of toxicity were 2,5DHA, cyperin, diospyrol, hypoxyphenone, lecanoric acid, orsellinic acid, prephenic acid, SDA, and O4BBA (Table 8). As they present no risk of toxicity and no violation of Lipinski's rules, these compounds were proposed as possible inhibitors of enzymes α -amylase, α -glucosidase, and pancreatic lipase enzyme. Therefore, they were evaluated in silico analysis to observe their performance as inhibitors, comparing them with the known inhibitors of these enzymes (acarbose for α -amylase and α -glucosidase and MUP for human pancreatic lipase). The bioavailability of

compounds present in lichens is assessed by topological polar surface area analysis (TPSA) (Torres-Benítez et al., 2022; Torres-Benítez et al., 2023a). This parameter is closely related to the passive molecular transport of drugs through cell membranes; it will allow predicting the behavior and properties of drug transport to assess their possible bioavailability. The TPSA parameter helped to predict the percentage absorption of the compounds (Torres-Benítez et al., 2022). The compounds that presented a higher percentage of absorption according to their TPSA values were 4-HSA (90.24%), O4BBA (90.24%), 18-HA (89.15%), cyperine (88, 67%), TOPA (83.39%), azelaic acid (83.26%), and phthalic acid (83.26%). With the results of the evaluation of the pharmacological and toxicological properties, it was observed that those compounds that did not present any toxicological risk and any violation of Lipinski's rules were proposed as possible inhibitors of the enzymes to be evaluated; therefore, the compounds 2,5DHA, cyperin, diospyrol, hypoxyphenone, lecanoric acid, orsellinic acid, prephenic acid, SDA, and O4BBA were those that were used for the in silico analysis to observe the behavior against these enzymes, comparing them with known inhibitors such as acarbose, orlistat, and MUP (Trang et al., 2017; Swargiary and Daimari, 2020).

Table 6- Analysis of pharmacokinetic property obtained from data software Osiris datawarrior programme of the phytochemicals obtained from the lichen based on lipsikins rule

Compound	%AB Sa	TPSA (Å ²)b	MWc	cLo gPd	HB De	HB Af	n-ROT Bg	Violation of Lipinski's rule
Rule	-	-	<500	≤5	≤5	≤10	≤10	≤1
18-HA	89.15	57.53	296.45	5.54	2	3	15	2
2,5DHA	69.30	115.06	198.13	-0.06	4	6	2	0
3,4DHA	82.17	77.76	154.12	0.45	3	4	1	0
TOPA	83.39	74.22	390.56	4.33	1	6	23	1
4-HSA	90.24	54.37	150.13	1.18	1	3	2	0
Azelaic acid	83.26	74.60	188.22	1.60	2	4	8	0
Crustinic acid	43.09	191.05	484.41	3.31	6	11	7	2
Cyperine	88.67	58.92	260.29	2.98	2	4	3	0
Diospyrol	81.08	80.92	346.38	5.01	4	4	1	0
Hypoxyphenone	80.08	83.83	210.18	1.16	2	5	3	0
Lecanoric acid	66.12	124.29	318.28	2.23	4	7	4	0
OBM	47.41	178.53	594.78	3.65	7	11	22	4
Orsellinic acid	82.17	77.76	168.15	0.80	3	4	1	0

Phthalic acid	83.26	74.60	166.13	0.63	2	4	2	0
Prephenic acid	70.39	111.9	226.18	-1.45	3	6	4	0
Rhein	70.39	111.9	284.22	1.83	3	6	1	0
SDA	65.12	127.2	358.30	2.19	2	8	9	0
Tetrafulcol A	25.25	242.76	498.40	2.49	12	12	3	2
Wedelolact one	71.27	109.36	314.25	2.43	3	7	1	0
O4BBA	90.24	54.37	302.33	3.93	1	3	4	0

3.17 Evaluation of docking α -amylase inhibition

Subsequent to the pharmacokinetic and toxicological analyses, those compounds that did not appear to be at any risk of toxicity, and no violation of Lipinski's rules were chosen (Figure 3). These compounds (Figure-3) were proposed as potential α -amylase inhibitors and evaluated by in silico molecular sugar analysis to investigate their behavior and binding properties at the α -amylase catalytic site (Figures 5, 6). The binding affinities of the compounds proposed as inhibitors and each of the enzymes. These compounds were compared with the reference inhibitor (acarbose) to see if the affinity at the catalytic site was similar or better. The study of the phytochemical-enzyme interaction showed that the compounds diospyrol, O4BBA, and lecanoric acid presented the highest binding affinities with the enzyme α -amylase. The binding affinities were found to be -9.00 , -8.70 , and -8.10 kcal/mol, respectively (Table 8). These affinities that these compounds appeared to have in comparison with the reference inhibitor acarbose (-7.80 kcal/mol) were higher because the map of ligand interactions (Figures 4C, E, I respectively) and the geometry adopted in the catalytic pocket (Figures 5C, E, I; respectively) were suitable for energetic and geometric stability at the catalytic site. The diospyrol compound presented two conventional H bonds with the amino acid Gln63 because the hydroxyl functional group of one of its aromatic rings allows the donation of a hydrogen bond as well as the acceptance of a hydrogen bond, and it is also observed that diospyrol presents a π -anion-type interaction between the π electrons of the aromatic ring and the amino acid Asp300. These interactions

are highly involved in the energetic and geometric stability of the diospyrol compound, so this compound had a higher binding affinity at the α -amylase catalytic site (Figure 5C). The compound O4BBA and lecanoric acid showed similar values in the binding affinity (-8.70 and -8.10 kcal/mol, respectively); however, it is observed that lecanoric acid has a lower binding affinity because it presents an unfavorable donor-donor interaction between a hydroxyl group of one of its aromatic rings and the amino acid His299; however, it is observed that it presents a higher binding affinity than the reference inhibitor acarbose because it presents three strong H-bond interactions with the amino acids Gln63, Asp197, and Asp300 (Figure 4E). Compounds SDA and cyperine presented binding affinities (-7.60 and -7.30 kcal/mol, respectively) similar to those of the reference inhibitor acarbose (-7.80 kcal/mol) because the geometric distribution (Figures 5B, H) and the interactions at the catalytic site (Figures 4B, H, respectively) were very similar to those of acarbose. Both compounds presented a strong H-bond-type interaction; the SDA compound interacted with His299 amino acid (Figure 4H), while the cyperine compound interacted with Asp300 amino acid (Figure 4B). The compounds 2.5DHA, hypoxyphenone, orselinic acid, and prephenic acid had similar and lower binding affinities (-6.10 , -6.00 , -6.10 , and -6.10 kcal/mol, respectively) compared to the inhibitor acarbose; this is mainly because the binding was carried out of the catalytic site of α -amylase, so the geometric distribution in the binding site was not the most adequate (Figures 4 A, D, F, G; respectively).

Figure 11 - Molecular interactions between phytochemicals and the α -amylase enzyme. (A) Molecular interactions of 2,5DHA and α -amylase; (B) molecular interactions of cyperine and α -amylase;(C) molecular interactions of diospyrol and α -amylase; (D) molecular interactions of hypoxyphenone and α -amylase; (E) molecular interactions of lecanoric acid and α -amylase; (F) molecular interactions of orsellinic and acid α -amylase; (G) molecular interactions of prephenic acid and α -amylase; (H) molecular interactions of SDA and α -amylase; and (I) molecular interactions of O4BBA and α - amylase.

Table -7 Binding affinities of phytochemicals with α -amylase, α -glucosidase, and human pancreatic lipase enzymes

Compound	α -Amylase (kcal/mol)	α -Glucosidase (kcal/mol)	pancreatic lipase (kcal/mol)
2,5DHA	-6.10	-5.80	-6.60
Cyperine	-7.30	-7.20	-8.10
Diospyrol	-9.00	-8.80	-11.0
Hypoxyphenone	-6.00	-4.90	-6.80
Lecanoric acid	-8.10	-7.00	-9.00
Orsellinic acid	-6.10	-5.10	-6.50
Prephenic acid	-6.10	-4.90	-6.50
SDA	-7.60	-7.30	-8.50
O4BBA	-8.70	-8.40	-10.5
Acarbose*	-7.80	-7.00	-
Orlistat*	-	-	-7.10
MUP*	-	-	-5.70

3.18 Evaluation of docking α -glucosidase inhibition

The results of the insilico analysis of the phytochemicals and α - glucosidase enzyme are shown in Figures 7. The compounds were compared with the reference inhibitor acarbose to see if the behavior of

the phytochemicals was similar or better against enzyme α - glucosidase. For each of the compounds, together with acarbose, their binding affinity (Table 8) against the α -glucosidase enzyme was calculated. It was observed that the compounds diospyrol and O4BBA presented higher binding affinities (-8.80 and -8.40 kcal/ mol, respectively) compared to the

reference inhibitor acarbose (-7.00 kcal/mol) (Table - 8). In the interaction map (Figure 8), it is observed that the diospyrol compound presented four H-bond-type interactions with the amino acids Asp197, Thr199, Asp437, and Asp536 (Figure 5C); in addition, this compound presented four π -anion-type interactions with the amino acids Asp197 and Asp536. These interactions presented by the compound diospyrol caused its affinity and geometry in the catalytic site to be more stable compared to the inhibitor acarbose (Figures 6C, 5C). The O4BBA compound presented three π -anion-type interactions between the π electrons of its aromatic rings and the amino acids Asp197, Asp437, and Asp536 (Figure 6I) which allow an electrostatic attraction at the catalytic site of α -glucosidase (Figure 5I). Five van der Waals-type interactions were also observed with the amino acids Arg196, Asp321, Met438, Ser442, Phe444, and Arg520. The compounds SDA, cyperine, and lecanoric acid presented binding affinities (-7.30 , -7.20 and -7.00 kcal/mol; respectively) similar to the inhibitor acarbose (-7.00 kcal/mol). The SDA compound presented two H-bond interactions, mainly

with the oxygens of the carbonyl groups and the amino acids Trp400 and Arg520 (Figure 8H). Two π -anion-type interactions were presented with the amino acids Trp400 and Tyr293. However, it was observed that the SDA compound presented two unfavorable negative-negative interactions with the amino acids Asp321 and Asp437; these interactions directly affect the energetic and geometric stability within the catalytic site of α -glucosidase (Figure 7H). Compounds showing lower binding affinities than acarbose were 2.5DHA, hypoxyphenone, orsellinic acid, and prephenic acid (-5.80 , -4.90 , -5.10 , and -4.90 kcal/mol, respectively). Of the compounds that presented lower affinities than acarbose, the one that presented important interactions in the catalytic site of α -glucosidase was 2.5DHA (Figures 5A, 6A). Three H-bond interactions were observed with the amino acids Asp437, Arg520, and His594 (Figure 5A). Two π -anion-type interactions were also observed between the π electrons of the aromatic ring and the amino acid Asp535 and the carboxylate with the amino acid Arg592.

Figure – 12 Molecular interactions between phytochemicals and the α -glucosidase enzyme. (A) Molecular interactions between 2,5DHA and α -glucosidase; (B) molecular interactions between cyperine and α -glucosidase; (C) molecular interactions between diospyrol and α -glucosidase;(D) molecular interactions between hypoxyphenone and α -glucosidase; (E) molecular interactions between lecanoric acid and α -glucosidase; (F) molecular interactions between orsellinic and acid α -glucosidase; (G) molecular interactions between prephenic acid and α -glucosidase; (H) molecular interactions between SDA and α -glucosidase; and (I) molecular interactions between O4BBA and α -glucosidase.

3.19 Evaluation of docking pancreatic lipase inhibition

To carry out the insilico analysis of the phytochemicals, the cocrystallized ligand (MUP) of the human pancreatic lipase enzyme was used, which was used as a reference compound for coupling and to determine the coordinates of the catalytic site of the enzyme to the compound orlistat as a reference inhibitor since it is the only drug approved by the FDA that acts on pancreatic lipase. The binding affinity results showed that the compounds cyperine, diospyrol, lecanoric acid, SDA, and O4BBA presented binding affinities (-8.10; -11.0; -9.00; -8.50, and -10.5 kcal/mol, respectively) higher than those of the reference inhibitors orlistat and MUP (-7.10 and -5.70 kcal/mol, respectively). This behavior is mainly because the geometry adopted by these compounds in the catalytic site of the enzyme allowed a better interaction with the amino acids directly involved in the catalytic sites (Ser152, Phe215, Arg256, His263, and Leu264). The diospyrol compound was the one that presented the highest binding affinity in the catalytic site because it presented two π -cation-type interactions between the π electrons of the aromatic ring and the amino acid His263, which is directly involved in the inhibition of human pancreatic lipase. In addition, five van der Waals interactions were observed with the amino acids Phe77, Asp79, Ser152, Leu153, Ile209, and Arg256 of which the amino acids Ser152 and Arg256 are directly involved in the enzyme binding site. The compound O4BBA was the second compound that presented a higher binding affinity in the human pancreatic lipase enzyme due to the conformation it adopted in the catalytic site. This compound presented two H-bond-type interactions with the amino acids Phe77 and Ser152; however, it also presented an unfavorable acceptor-acceptor interaction with the amino acid Ser152, causing it to have an interaction similar to that of the diospyrol compound. The compounds cyperine, lecanoric acid, and SDA showed similar conformations and binding affinities at the catalytic site of human pancreatic lipase. This behavior is mainly because they presented similar interactions with the residues directly involved in the catalytic site. The cyperine compound presented three H-bond-type interactions with the amino acids Phe77, Asp79, and Arg256; in addition, it presented attractive

charge-type interactions between two carboxylate groups and a hydroxyl with the amino acids His151, His263, and Arg256. These interactions allowed adequate stabilization at the binding site. Figure 10E shows the main interactions presented by the lecanoric acid compound against the human pancreatic lipase enzyme. This compound presented some H-bond interactions with the amino acid Arg256 and five van der Waals-type interactions with the amino acids Phe77, Asp79, Ala178, Ile209, and His263. The SDA compound presented three H-bond interactions with the amino acids Phe77, Ser152, and Arg256. It also presented two attractive charge-type interactions with the amino acids Arg256 and His263. These interactions with the amino acids that were in the binding site allowed the conformation of the SDA compound to stabilize and have better binding affinity with the reference inhibitors (orlistat and MUP). According to molecular docking analyses, there is a greater potential for pharmacological effect when evaluating isolated compounds present in the extracts of *Psoroma* species, which is evident with other lichen species, such as *H. lugubris* where the isolation of compounds such as usnic acid, barbatolic acid, atranol, and 5,7-dihydroxy-6-methylphthalide demonstrates greater antioxidant and enzyme inhibition activity (Areche et al., 2022); likewise, computational studies carried out with compounds present in the extracts of other Antarctic species, such as *L. brialmontii*, *P. pubescens*, *S. globosus*, *C. gracilis*, and *C. chlorophaea* (Torres-Benítez et al., 2022; Torres-Benítez et al., 2023a), validate the promising use of compounds of phenolic nature for the treatment of different pathologies of wide prevalence and incidence as well as the understanding of their mechanisms of action at the organismic and cellular level (White et al., 2014). In addition, in the last 2 decades, biologically active metabolites have been isolated, such as atranorin (Melo et al., 2011; Zhou et al., 2017; Urbanska et al., 2022), barbatic acid (Reddy et al., 2019), diffractaic acid (Karagoz et al., 2015; Emsen et al., 2018), evernic acid (Fernandez-Moriano et al., 2017a; Shameera Ahamed et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2021), fumarprotocetraric acid (Kosanić et al., 2014; Fernández-Moriano et al., 2017b), gyrophoric acid (Candan et al., 2006; Bačkorová et al., 2011), lobaric acid (Hong et al., 2018), physodic acid (Studzińska-Sroka et al., 2021b), protocetraric acid (Nguyen et al., 2023), thamnolan (Omarsdottir et

al., 2007), usnic acid (Luzina and Salakhutdinov, 2018), and vulpinic acid (Varol et al., 2016; Kılıç et al., 2018), which are present in the species of the

genera *Cladonia*, *Parmotrema*, *Lepraria*, *Lethariella*, *Pseudoevernia*, *Hypotrachyna*, *Umbilicaria*, *Usnea*, among others.

Figure – 13 Docking molecular between phytochemicals and the α -glucosidase enzyme in a surface view. (A) α -Glucosidase and 2,5DHA; (B) α -glucosidase and cyperine; (C) α -glucosidase and diospyrol; (D) α -glucosidase and hypoxyphenone; (E) α -glucosidase and lecanoric acid; (F) α -glucosidase and orsellinic acid; (G) α -glucosidase and prephenic acid; (H) α -glucosidase and SDA; and (I) α -glucosidase and O4BBA

Figure 14 - Molecular interactions between phytochemicals and the human pancreatic lipase enzyme. (A) Molecular interactions between 2,5DHA and pancreatic lipase; (B) cyperine and pancreatic lipase; (C) diospyrol and pancreatic lipase; (D) hypoxyphenone and pancreatic lipase; (E) lecanoric acid and pancreatic lipase; (F) orsellinic and pancreatic lipase; (G) prephenic acid and human pancreatic lipase; (H) SDA and human pancreatic lipase; and (I) O4BBA and pancreatic lipase.

DISCUSSION

This work provides the first comprehensive evaluation of Nilgiris lichen extracts as multi-target inhibitors relevant to diabetes management. While earlier studies have reported isolated antioxidant or enzyme inhibitory activities of lichens, our findings extend this knowledge by demonstrating concurrent inhibition of four major therapeutic targets— α -amylase, α -glucosidase, pancreatic lipase, and PTP1B. This multi-target profile is particularly significant, as it addresses both postprandial hyperglycemia and insulin resistance, offering a broader therapeutic advantage compared to single-target natural agents. Importantly, GC-MS and docking analyses identified compounds such as diisopyrol, O-(4-biphenylcarbonyl) benzoic acid, and lecanoric acid with higher binding affinities than standard drugs like acarbose and orlistat. These compounds were Lipinski-compliant and non-toxic in silico, reinforcing their translational potential as drug-like leads. Such findings highlight the uniqueness of Nilgiris lichens, which remain largely uncharacterized in antidiabetic research compared to better-studied genera from temperate regions. The integrated workflow combining phytochemical profiling, in vitro enzyme assays, and computational validation demonstrates novelty not only in the compounds identified but also in the strategy applied. This positions our study as a blueprint for discovering and validating multi-target natural therapeutics from underexplored ecological niches. Further in vivo studies and isolation of pure metabolites will be critical to advance these findings toward clinical relevance.

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